

Tracer study of BS in Information Technology (BSIT) graduates of St. Dominic College of Asia from 2010 to 2021

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Abstract

The quality of education students receive in the schools, colleges, and universities where they are enrolled depends on the assistance and knowledge of quality teachers and professors, whose duty is to impart to the students the knowledge and experience that they themselves have also amassed in their many years of teaching. Tracer studies improve the marketability of educational programs and the relevance of the curriculum. Every educational institution should be in the position of keeping track of its graduates since this serves as a benchmark to see whether the lessons learned over the years of enrollment have been put to good use and have benefited the students as well. It will also show how successful the institution is and how dedicated it is to provide educational excellence. This study determines the employability of Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) graduates of St. Dominic College of Asia in the academic years 2010 to 2021 and highlighted specifically their personal profile in terms of gender and status of employment as well as location wherein they are employed, pursuance of graduate studies, type of industry they are involved in, relevance of college experience to employment, and duration to how long they are employed. The study used a descriptive method. The data gathered was through a questionnaire made in Google Forms and was given to 210 respondents deployed through a social media platform and the results were statistically treated using averaging and percentage. It was found out through this tracer study that most graduates were male, self-employed, most did not pursue a graduate degree or vocational course / certificate and held to their jobs for more than four years. There is also strong evidence that what they experience in college held relevance to their current employment.

Keywords: *Tracer study; BSIT graduates; St. Dominic College of Asia.*

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Introduction

Tracer studies are a way to keep the curriculum updated and offer graduates specific benefits to increase the marketability of educational programs (Cuadra et al., 2019). A sufficient understanding of the employment outcomes of training graduates could help in the formulation of policies to address issues like unemployment (Jackson, 2013; Nazron et al., 2017). Students must gain a sense of competence in their chosen industry and build their confidence to explore new opportunities and new careers, especially considering the growing rivalry among coworkers (Tutor et al., 2021). Higher education institutions must demonstrate that finding a job is not difficult for their graduates. The current level of company or corporate competitiveness is quite high due to the market's rising demand. Only a select handful get hired, demonstrating that these fortunate applicants are the best of the best. One must essentially possess proficiency in each of the three domains, such as the knowledge, abilities, and attitudes necessary for the work, especially if they are information technology graduates.

Several studies determined the value and applicability of their graduate studies to their positions and the field (Almejas et al., 2017; Reusia et al., 2020; Reyes & Salas, 2021; Woya, 2019). The survey they conducted is the first of its kind, in such a way that, the first of its sort in the seven years of its programs, asked for comments on the kind of duties and responsibilities done by the graduates in their separate employment as well as information on how valuable and pertinent their degrees were to the work they were doing. In connection with this, the graduates were asked to provide some recommendations on whether the institution should provide information technology-related graduate programs so that they could have the option to continue their studies at the same institution if they wanted.

Balingbing (2014) conducted a study on the employability of BSIT graduates, focusing on their personal profile, level of competency across knowledge, skills, and attitudes, the significant relationship between the level of competency and the level of challenges across knowledge, skills, and attitudes, and measures to increase their competitiveness. In her study, she found out that there is no significant relationship between the level of competencies among graduates per school year and their level of difficulty with knowledge, skills, and attitudes. In a related study by Mina et al. (2020), which aimed at the general characteristics, educational background, and passed professional examinations of the unwaged respondents' post-college employment profiles and reasons for unemployment, there is a relationship between the high rate of employability and regular or permanent status. This indicates that the BSIT program is in line with what is required by the industry based on the updated curriculum.

This study was conducted because St. Dominic College of Asia is committed to creating BSIT graduates who can compete internationally. The employability of BSIT graduates from the academic years 2010 to 2021 is assessed in this study. Particularly, their gender, job status, and place of employment; their pursuit of graduate degrees; the industry they work in; the applicability of their college experience to employment; and the length of their employment are the variables that this study focused on.

Objectives of the Study

This study determines the employability of BSIT graduates from the academic years 2010 to 2021, respectively. Specifically, their personal profile in terms of gender, status of employment as well as location wherein they are employed, pursuance of graduate studies, type of industry they are involved in, relevance of college experience to employment, and duration of how long they are employed.

Conceptual Framework

The input-process-output (IPO) system approach is adopted in this study. It consists of four (4) major parts, namely: input, processing, output, and feedback.

Input: The researcher considered the following variables in preparing the data to be collected in the online survey questionnaire: a) profile of BSIT graduates in terms of gender and year graduated; b) status of employment of BSIT graduates; c) employment duration of BSIT graduates; d) location of employment of the BSIT graduates; e) type of industry that the BSIT graduates are employed in; f) postgraduate studies or advanced training of BSIT graduates; and g) relevance of college experience to the current employment of BSIT graduates.

Process: Obtaining the list of BSIT graduates from the registrar's office and the distribution of the online questionnaire by contacting and researching their names through social media and directly messaging them to participate in the online questionnaire made through Google Forms and an unstructured interview of the respondents as part of the process. After which, researchers tabulated the results gathered starting from the months of May to October 2021.

Output: Organizing the tabulated results according to the variables asked in the questionnaire and computing the averages and percentages to interpret the distribution of the data.

Feedback: When the questionnaire is revised or altered, feedback is given. If there is a problem with the output that requires modifications or adjustments in the queries, it may return to the input stage or to the process stage.

Methods

The descriptive approach of research was deemed appropriate for this study's execution. The researcher conducted this study by adhering to several standard practices. First, when the research idea was presented and approved by the BSIT chairperson, the researcher promptly asked permission to proceed with the study. Second, questionnaires that had been produced online via Google Docs and validated were delivered to the graduates via social media, regular mail, and other channels. A note was included with the questionnaire to explain the study and reassure the respondents that their answers would be kept private. Third, the researcher collected the completed surveys. Fourth, an analysis of the collected data using numbers was done. Finally, consolidations of the key findings in response to the queries were taken into consideration. The respondents of the study were supposed to consist of 220 BSIT graduates from batches 2010–2021. However, there were only 210 responses from the questionnaires obtained, or a retrieval rate of 95.5%. The collected data were all presented quantitatively. The statistical tools used were averaging and percentage calculation.

Results and Discussion

The profile of the respondents is the first piece of data discussed. Gender and the year of graduation were the only attributes of the student profile deemed significant to be obtained in this study. The total number of graduates of the BSIT program at St. Dominic College of Asia from AY 2010 to 2021 was 220, and only 210 responses from the online survey were obtained, or a 95.5% retrieval rate.

As shown in Table 1, there were 83, or 39.5 percent, female and 127, or 60.5 percent, male graduates of the BSIT program at St. Dominic College of Asia among the total 210 respondents. The graduates were highly dominated by males. Also, as seen from this table, there were fewer BSIT graduates after the academic year 2017 compared to the previous academic years before 2017. The highest number of graduated students from an academic year is 30 from academic years 2012 and 2016, respectively, while the lowest academic year to have the least number of graduates was in 2020.

Table 1. Profile of BSIT Graduates in Terms of Gender

Year Graduated	Female		Male		Total
	f	%	f	%	
2010	1	25.0	3	75.0	4
2011	9	45.0	11	55.0	20
2012	12	40.0	18	60.0	30
2013	9	37.5	15	62.5	24
2014	8	44.4	10	55.6	18
2015	10	41.7	14	58.3	24
2016	12	40.0	18	60.0	30
2017	5	31.3	11	68.8	16
2018	5	31.3	11	68.8	16
2019	8	40.0	12	60.0	20
2020	1	50.0	1	50.0	2
2021	3	50.0	3	50.0	6
Total	83	39.5	127	60.5	210

Table 2 represents the status of employment of the BSIT graduate respondents. It is shown that 89, or 42.4%, of the graduates do have regular jobs. Self-employed BSIT graduates are at 48, or 22.9%.

Probationary BSIT graduates are at 40, or 19.0%. Contractual BSIT graduates are at 14, or 6.7%. Upper management BSIT graduates are at 10, or 4.8%, while middle management graduates are at 9, or 4.3%. This clearly shows that although there are still contractual and probationary jobs acquired by the BSIT graduates, the majority will eventually become regular employees, and a good number of them can reach middle and upper management.

Table 2. Status of Employment of BSIT Graduates (n = 210)

Category	Frequency	Percent
Contractual / Temporary	14	6.7
Probationary	40	19.0
Regular	89	42.4
Self-employed	48	22.9
Middle Management	9	4.3
Upper Management	10	4.8

Table 3 represents the data acquired regarding the employment duration of the BSIT graduates. It is shown that 47, or 22.4%, of the graduates hold on to their current employment for more than four years. It was followed by 40, or 19.0%, who had jobs for only one to six months. It is then followed by 36, or 17.1%, who had two to less than three years of employment. Behind it were 33, or 15.7%, BSIT graduates who stood by their employment for seven to 11 months. After which, there were 30 or 14.3% of BSIT graduates who stood by their employment for one to less than two years. Lastly, there were 24 people, or 11.4%, who had been employed for three to less than four years. Based upon this data, it can be observed that the majority of BSIT graduates of St. Dominic College of Asia did not stay long in their temporary employment but rather have much longer permanent jobs, as seen from the number of graduates who spent longer years in their current employment.

Table 3. Employment Duration of BSIT Graduates (n = 210)

Category	Frequency	Percent
1 month to 6 months	40	19.0
7 months to 11 months	33	15.7
1 year to less than 2 years	30	14.3
2 years to less than 3 years	36	17.1
3 years to less than 4 years	24	11.4
More than 4 years	47	22.4

Table 4 represents the tabulated data on the location of employment of the BSIT graduates. It can be shown from the data obtained from the online survey that 190 BSIT graduates, or 90.5%, are employed locally, while the remaining 20, or 9.5%, are employed abroad. It can be interpreted from this data that although the majority is employed locally, there is still a significant number of graduates who have been accepted to be employed abroad.

Table 4. Employment Duration of BSIT Graduates (n = 210)

Category	Frequency	Percent
Local	190	90.5
Abroad	20	9.5

Table 5 represents the tabulated data on the type of industry in which the BSIT graduates are employed. The information technology industry took the lead, as 97, or 46.2%, of the BSIT graduates are employed in that area. It was followed by 36, or 17.1%, employees in the business process outsourcing (BPO) industry. Closely trailing is the marketing industry, with 34, or 16.2%, BSIT graduates employed. A significant gap from 34 to 15, or 7.1%, of BSIT graduates is in the health and services industry. Trailing behind is the finance industry, with 14 or 6.7% employed BSIT graduates. Lastly, in the education sector, 11 or 5.2% of BSIT graduates were employed in this industry. Although there are still a significant number

of BSIT graduates employed in the BPO industry, it can be seen from the data obtained that a great majority of the graduates are employed in the industry they are aligned with, which is the information technology industry. It cannot be dismissed that the marketing industry or sales can be an alternative to be employed in, based on the respondents. Sadly, only a small number of BSIT students chose to follow and pursue the education industry, with about 5.2% based upon the responses from the survey.

Table 5. Type of Industry that the BSIT Graduates are Employed (n = 210)

Category	Frequency	Percent
Business Process Outsourcing	36	17.1
Education	11	5.2
Finance	14	6.7
Marketing	34	16.2
Health and Services	15	7.1
Information technology	97	46.2
Others	3	1.4

Table 6 represents the tabulated data on which postgraduate studies and advanced training were pursued by the BSIT students after they graduated from the BSIT program at St. Dominic College of Asia. It can be seen from the table that only 20 of the 9.5% of the BSIT graduates pursued a vocational course or certification. Only five (5), or 2.4%, got a master’s degree, while the rest of the 185, or 88.1%, felt satisfied with their current education and did not pursue further studies after graduation.

Table 6. Postgraduate Studies / Advanced Training of BSIT Graduates

Category	Frequency	Percent
Vocational Course / Certifications	20	9.5
Master’s Degree	5	2.4
Doctorate Degree	0	0.0
Not Applicable	185	88.1

Table 7 represents the tabulated responses of the BSIT graduates, wherein they expressed the relevance of their college experience to their current employment. It can be seen from the tabulated data that, with a total of 191 respondents, or 91.0%, the majority of the BSIT graduates that participated in the survey felt that their college experience has a great influence on their current employment, while 19 respondents, or 9.0%, felt their college experience has no relevance to their current employment. From the data retrieved, it can be concluded that being a BSIT graduate really has a weight on their current employment status, and the institution of St. Dominic College of Asia has a strong BSIT program.

Table 7. Relevance of College Experience to the Current Employment of BSIT Graduates

Category	Frequency	Percent
Yes	191	91.0
No	19	9.0

Conclusions and Recommendations

It is safe to say that the BSIT program at St. Dominic College of Asia is not easy and can be ranked as one of the most difficult programs offered in the institution because of the fast-paced updates of software applications and new hardware technologies that are being created, along with the vast majority of programming languages that are available in the IT industry. Despite difficulties in knowledge, skills, and attitudes, BSIT graduates of St. Dominic College of Asia were still employed due to the diverse industries available and the need for IT workers.

The proposed measures to improve the BSIT program are deemed necessary for the program's graduates' advancement. Based upon the study conducted, the majority of the BSIT graduates are employed aligned to their program, which can prove that the BSIT program at St. Dominic College of Asia is doing well. Though there are still some who are not employed, measures can still be implemented, and the curriculum is continually evaluated and updated on a regular basis. A student and faculty development program should be developed and implemented to improve faculty and student knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Future research must follow up on the proposed measures to improve graduate competency.

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